

Four and Five Figures of Kifilideen (Power of Base 11) and Antikifilideen (Antipower of Base 11) Tables as a Tool For Mathematics Computation

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ABSTRACT

The four-figure of power of base numbers of tables needs to be created for easy synchronization with the existing Logarithm table of power of base 10 which is working on four figures. Although the five-figure of power base numbers of tables are more accurate because it is having less approximation in its establishment. The four-figure table is easy to compute doing utilization because it is having less digits to work with. This paper presents the four and five figures of Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables for the computation of mathematical problems. The four and five figures are both reliable to work with. However, there is a tradeoff between easy computation as related to the four-figure table and more accuracy as related to the five-figure table in their utilization.

Keywords: AntiKifilideen Table, Computation, Kifilideen Table, Logarithm Table, Power of base 11.

1. INTRODUCTION

Umbarger (2006); Burton (2007); and Roegel (2010) indicate that the word logarithm was derived from Portmanteau word. Napier (1550 – 1617), who coined the term bring it up has “reckoning number,” which means the number of ratios used. More so, Stein (2004), Benezovski (2007) and Kopp (2020) present that Napier casted the word logarithm from two Greek words (*logos* and *arithmos* which mean ratio/logic and number respectively). Although, Weber (2016) states that the meaning of the term logarithm is not self – evident; nor is the meaning of its etymological translation: ‘ratio number’. Napier further elucidated his work as follows: the geometric progression $1, n, n^2, \dots$ have a common ratio, n . If the arithmetic progression $0, 1, 2, \dots$ positioned onto this progression, the sequences of the arithmetic progression indicate how often the 1 of the first term of the geometric progression was multiplied by the common ratio n . After speaking of ‘artificial number,’ he later called the numbers of the arithmetic progression the ‘number of ratios,’ or logarithm. This means that, the ‘number that counts ratios’ of 81 to base 3 is 4, because 1 must be multiplied by 3 four time to produce 81 that is $1 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 = 81$. This makes Logarithms to be referred to as repeated divisions (Espedal 2015; Vos and Espedal, 2016; Kuper and Carlson, 2020). The ideology behind logarithms as numbers that count

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divisions was widespread during the 17th century but became less dominant in later definitions of logarithms (Katz, 1997; Navarro – Loidi and Llombart, 2008; Weber, 2019).

Since the days of Euler (1707 – 1788), logarithms have been made parts of school curricula (Okoye – Ogbalu, 2019). It remained pertinent in schools for centuries until the establishment of pocket calculators (Szpiro, 2014). Kenney and Kastberg (2015) stated that logarithms continue to play a vital role despite the existence of calculators which as presently taking over computational part involving logarithms (Smith, 2000; Liang and Wood, 2005; Stoll, 2006). In West Africa, logarithm is included in the school curriculum for both Mathematics and Further mathematics in which students are evaluated often on it in their West Africa Examination Certificate (WAEC) examination and in Nigeria, NECO Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination also examined the understanding of candidates on the topic Logarithm (Estapa and Nadolny, 2015; Moyinoluwa, 2015; Ndlovu, 2016; Udofia and Udoh, 2017). Furthermore, in Nigeria, the use of logarithm is much indispensable and crucial (Nichos and Thomas, 1998). Logarithm is taught starting from senior secondary school level one (science, commercial and art classes) up to university level precisely 100 level (Rafi and Retnawati, 2018). Till today logarithm is a core concept for many University and Polytechnic mathematical courses including calculus, differential equations, and complex analysis (Weber, 2002).

The four-figure of power of base numbers of tables need to be created for easy synchronization with existing Logarithm table of power of base 10 which is working on four figures. Although the five figure of power base numbers of tables are more accurate because it is having less approximation in its establishment. The four-figure table is easy to compute doing utilization because it is having less digit to work with. This paper presents the four and five figures of Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables for the computation of mathematical problem.

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology in the establishment of the four figures table of Kifilideen (Power of Base 11) table is provided in detail. Tables 1-4 present the establishment of four figure of Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables while Tables 4-8 indicate the five figures of Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables. The Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables were

inaugurated based on manual method of computing and with the assistance of calculator (Osanyinpeju et al., 2019). However, the tables can be used to solve modern real-life problem without the use of calculator. The genesis of the manual method used to construct these tables mentioned above is demonstrated as follows: To convert 41 to the power of base 11, you start by looking for the value to be raised by 11 to give 44. $11^1 = 11$ which is less than the 44 to be achieved. Then, the power of the base three is increased. So, we try 11^2 which gives 121. The value obtained is greater than the value we needed that is 44. Then, the power is reduced to 1.5. Meanwhile, $11^{1.5} = 36.4829$. This value attained is getting closer to the required value. So, $11^{1.57}$ is tried which gives 43.1506 but $11^{1.58}$ gives 44.1978. The power is then given a 3 decimal places trial. For $11^{1.578}$ we have 43.9863 but $11^{1.579}$ produces 44.0919. With this power 1.578, we are almost there. We go for power of 4 decimal places. Trying $11^{1.5781}$ we obtained 43.9969. Trying $11^{1.5782}$ we obtained 44.0074. For 5 decimal places, $11^{1.57813}$ gives 44.0000. For four figure table $11^{1.5781}$ or $11^{1.5782}$ gives 43.9969 or 44.0074 ≈ 44 while for five figure table $11^{1.57813}$ gives exact 44. Since the table was constructed base on power of 4 and 5 decimal places. So, the four figures power in which 11 must be raised to give 44 is 1.5781 indicating $Kif(44)$ is 1.5781 or $44 = 11^{Kif(44)} = 11^{1.5781}$. So, the five figures power in which 11 must be raised to give 44 is 1.57813 indicating $Kif(44)$ is 1.57813 or $44 = 11^{Kif(44)} = 11^{1.57813}$. The five figures of Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables had been in existing and was first published in 2019 (Osanyinpeju 2019; Osanyinpeju, 2020).

Table 1. Kifilideen (Power of base 11) of number in Four Figure $x \rightarrow Kif x$.

(x)											Difference								
	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	0.0000	0.0397	0.0760	0.1094	0.1403	0.1691	0.1960	0.2213	0.2451	0.2677	30	60	89	118	147	176	205	233	261
2	0.2891	0.3094	0.3288	0.3474	0.3651	0.3821	0.3985	0.4142	0.4294	0.4440	17	34	51	68	85	102	119	136	152
3	0.4582	0.4718	0.4851	0.4979	0.5104	0.5224	0.5342	0.5456	0.5567	0.5676	12	24	36	48	60	72	86	96	108
4	0.5781	0.5884	0.5985	0.6083	0.6179	0.6272	0.6364	0.6454	0.6542	0.6628	9	19	28	37	47	56	65	75	84
5	0.6712	0.6794	0.6875	0.6955	0.7033	0.7109	0.7184	0.7258	0.7331	0.7402	8	15	23	31	38	46	53	61	68
6	0.7472	0.7541	0.7609	0.7676	0.7741	0.7806	0.7870	0.7932	0.7994	0.8055	6	13	19	26	32	39	45	52	58
7	0.8115	0.8174	0.8233	0.8290	0.8347	0.8403	0.8458	0.8513	0.8566	0.8619	6	11	17	22	28	34	39	45	50
8	0.8672	0.8724	0.8775	0.8825	0.8875	0.8925	0.8974	0.9022	0.9069	0.9117	5	10	15	20	25	30	34	39	44
9	0.9163	0.9209	0.9255	0.9300	0.9344	0.9389	0.9432	0.9476	0.9518	0.9561	4	9	13	18	22	26	31	35	40
10	0.9603	0.9644	0.9685	0.9726	0.9766	0.9806	0.9846	0.9885	0.9923	0.9962	4	8	12	16	20	24	28	32	36
11	1.0000	1.0038	1.0075	1.0112	1.0149	1.0185	1.0221	1.0257	1.0293	1.0328	4	7	11	15	18	22	25	29	33
12	1.0363	1.0397	1.0432	1.0466	1.0500	1.0533	1.0566	1.0599	1.0632	1.0664	3	7	10	13	17	20	23	27	30
13	1.0697	1.0729	1.0760	1.0792	1.0823	1.0854	1.0885	1.0915	1.0946	1.0976	3	6	9	12	15	19	22	25	28
14	1.1006	1.1035	1.1065	1.1094	1.1123	1.1152	1.1181	1.1209	1.1237	1.1266	3	6	9	12	14	17	20	23	26
15	1.1293	1.1321	1.1349	1.1376	1.1403	1.1430	1.1457	1.1484	1.1510	1.1536	3	5	8	11	13	16	19	22	24
16	1.1563	1.1589	1.1614	1.1640	1.1666	1.1691	1.1716	1.1741	1.1766	1.1791	3	5	8	10	13	15	18	20	23

0.61	4.3177	4.3280	4.3384	4.3488	4.3593	4.3697	4.3802	4.3908	4.4013	4.4119	1	0	1	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0.62	4.4225	4.4331	4.4437	4.4544	4.4651	4.4758	4.4865	4.4973	4.5081	4.5189	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.63	4.5298	4.5407	4.5516	4.5625	4.5734	4.5844	4.5954	4.6065	4.6175	4.6286	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.64	4.6397	4.6509	4.6620	4.6732	4.6844	4.6957	4.7070	4.7183	4.7296	4.7409	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.65	4.7523	4.7637	4.7752	4.7866	4.7981	4.8096	4.8212	4.8328	4.8444	4.8560	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.66	4.8676	4.8793	4.8910	4.9028	4.9146	4.9264	4.9382	4.9500	4.9619	4.9738	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.67	4.9858	4.9977	5.0097	5.0218	5.0338	5.0459	5.0580	5.0702	5.0823	5.0945	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.68	5.1068	5.1190	5.1313	5.1436	5.1560	5.1684	5.1808	5.1932	5.2057	5.2182	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.69	5.2307	5.2433	5.2559	5.2685	5.2811	5.2938	5.3065	5.3193	5.3320	5.3448	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.70	5.3577	5.3705	5.3834	5.3963	5.4093	5.4223	5.4353	5.4483	5.4614	5.4745	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.71	5.4877	5.5009	5.5141	5.5273	5.5406	5.5539	5.5672	5.5806	5.5940	5.6074	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.72	5.6209	5.6344	5.6479	5.6614	5.6750	5.6887	5.7023	5.716	5.7297	5.7435	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.73	5.7573	5.7711	5.7849	5.7988	5.8128	5.8267	5.8407	5.8547	5.8688	5.8829	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.74	5.8970	5.9111	5.9253	5.9396	5.9538	5.9681	5.9824	5.9968	6.0112	6.0256	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.75	6.0401	6.0546	6.0691	6.0837	6.0983	6.1130	6.1276	6.1423	6.1571	6.1719	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.76	6.1867	6.2015	6.2164	6.2314	6.2463	6.2613	6.2763	6.2914	6.3065	6.3217	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.77	6.3368	6.3520	6.3673	6.3826	6.3979	6.4133	6.4287	6.4441	6.4596	6.4751	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.78	6.4906	6.5062	6.5218	6.5375	6.5532	6.5689	6.5847	6.6005	6.6163	6.6322	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.79	6.6481	6.6641	6.6801	6.6961	6.7122	6.7283	6.7445	6.7607	6.7769	6.7932	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.80	6.8095	6.8258	6.8422	6.8586	6.8751	6.8916	6.9082	6.9247	6.9414	6.9580	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.81	6.9747	6.9915	7.0083	7.0251	7.0420	7.0589	7.0758	7.0928	7.1098	7.1269	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.82	7.1440	7.1612	7.1784	7.1956	7.2129	7.2302	7.2475	7.2649	7.2824	7.2999	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.83	7.3174	7.3350	7.3526	7.3702	7.3879	7.4056	7.4234	7.4412	7.4591	7.4770	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.84	7.4950	7.5130	7.5310	7.5491	7.5672	7.5854	7.6036	7.6218	7.6401	7.6585	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.85	7.6769	7.6953	7.7138	7.7323	7.7509	7.7695	7.7881	7.8068	7.8256	7.8443	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.86	7.8632	7.8820	7.9010	7.9199	7.9390	7.9580	7.9771	7.9963	8.0155	8.0347	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.87	8.0540	8.0733	8.0927	8.1121	8.1316	8.1511	8.1707	8.1903	8.2100	8.2297	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.88	8.2495	8.2693	8.2891	8.3090	8.3290	8.3490	8.3690	8.3891	8.4092	8.4294	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.89	8.4497	8.4700	8.4903	8.5107	8.5311	8.5516	8.5721	8.5927	8.6133	8.6340	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.90	8.6547	8.6755	8.6963	8.7172	8.7381	8.7591	8.7801	8.8012	8.8224	8.8435	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.91	8.8648	8.8860	8.9074	8.9288	8.9502	8.9717	8.9932	9.0148	9.0365	9.0582	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.92	9.0799	9.1017	9.1236	9.1455	9.1674	9.1894	9.2115	9.2336	9.2558	9.2780	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.93	9.3003	9.3226	9.3450	9.3674	9.3899	9.4124	9.4350	9.4577	9.4804	9.5032	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.94	9.5260	9.5488	9.5718	9.5947	9.6178	9.6409	9.6640	9.6872	9.7105	9.7338	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.95	9.7572	9.7806	9.8041	9.8276	9.8512	9.8748	9.8985	9.9223	9.9461	9.9700	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.96	9.9939	10.0179	10.0419	10.0661	10.0903	10.1145	10.1388	10.1631	10.1875	10.2120	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
0.97	10.2365	10.2611	10.2857	10.3104	10.3351	10.3600	10.3848	10.4098	10.4347	10.4598	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0

0.98	10.4849	10.5101	10.53532	10.5606	10.5860	10.6114	10.6369	10.6624	10.6880	10.7136	2	5	7	1	1	1	1	2	2
0.99	10.7394	10.7652	10.7910	10.8169	10.8429	10.8689	10.8950	10.9212	10.9474	10.9737	2	5	7	1	1	1	1	2	2
											6	2	8	4	0	6	2	8	5

Table 4. Conversion of 11^y to 10^n in Four Figures $11^y \rightarrow 10^n$.

11^y	10^n												
1	1.0414	16	16.6623	31	32.2832	46	47.9041	61	63.5250	76	79.1458	91	94.7667
2	2.0828	17	17.7037	32	33.3246	47	48.9455	62	64.5663	77	80.1872	92	95.8081
3	3.1242	18	18.7451	33	34.3660	48	49.9868	63	65.6077	78	81.2286	93	96.8495
4	4.1656	19	19.7865	34	35.4074	49	51.0282	64	66.6491	79	82.2700	94	97.8909
5	5.2070	20	20.8279	35	36.4487	50	52.0696	65	67.6905	80	83.3114	95	98.9323
6	6.2484	21	21.8692	36	37.4901	51	53.1110	66	68.7319	81	84.3528	96	99.9737
7	7.2897	22	22.9106	37	38.5315	52	54.1524	67	69.7733	82	85.3942	97	101.0151
8	8.3311	23	23.9520	38	39.5729	53	55.1938	68	70.8147	83	86.4356	98	102.0565
9	9.3725	24	24.9934	39	40.6143	54	56.2352	69	71.8561	84	87.4770	99	103.0979
10	10.4139	25	26.0348	40	41.6557	55	57.2766	70	72.8975	85	88.5184		
11	11.4553	26	27.0762	41	42.6971	56	58.3180	71	73.9389	86	89.5598		
12	12.4967	27	28.1176	42	43.7385	57	59.3594	72	74.9803	87	90.6012		
13	13.5381	28	29.1590	43	44.7799	58	60.4008	73	76.0217	88	91.6426		
14	14.5795	29	30.2004	44	45.8213	59	61.4422	74	77.0631	89	92.6839		
15	15.6209	30	31.2418	45	46.8627	60	62.4836	75	78.1045	90	93.7253		

Table 5. Kifilideen (Power of base 11) of number in Five Figure $x \rightarrow Kifx$.

(x)											Differences								
	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	0	0.03975	0.07603	0.10941	0.14032	0.16909	0.19601	0.22129	0.24513	0.26767	2	5	8	1	1	1	2	2	2
2	0.28906	0.30941	0.32881	0.34735	0.36510	0.38212	0.39848	0.41422	0.42938	0.44402	9	9	8	8	7	5	4	5	1
3	0.45816	0.47183	0.48507	0.49790	0.51035	0.52244	0.53419	0.54562	0.55674	0.56757	9	5	9	1	1	9	5	1	1
4	0.57813	0.58843	0.59848	0.60829	0.61788	0.62725	0.63641	0.64538	0.65416	0.66276	7	4	1	8	5	2	9	7	2
5	0.67119	0.67845	0.68754	0.69549	0.70328	0.71094	0.71845	0.72583	0.73308	0.74021	2	3	4	5	4	3	1	3	5
6	0.74722	0.75411	0.76090	0.76757	0.77414	0.78060	0.78697	0.79324	0.79942	0.80551	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	0
7	0.81151	0.81742	0.82326	0.82901	0.83468	0.84028	0.84580	0.85125	0.85664	0.86195	9	8	7	6	6	5	5	3	3
8	0.86719	0.87238	0.87749	0.88255	0.88754	0.89248	0.89735	0.90218	0.90694	0.91165	4	8	1	5	8	1	4	5	8
9	0.91631	0.92092	0.92548	0.92999	0.93445	0.93886	0.94323	0.94755	0.95183	0.95606	7	5	3	3	4	5	6	6	6
10	0.96025	0.96440	0.96851	0.97258	0.97661	0.98060	0.98455	0.98847	0.99235	0.99619	7	3	0	6	2	8	4	6	5
11	1.00000	1.00377	1.00751	1.01122	1.0149	1.01853	1.02215	1.02573	1.02928	1.03280	6	3	7	0	4	8	1	5	9
12	1.03629	1.03975	1.04318	1.04658	1.04996	1.05331	1.05663	1.05993	1.0632	1.06645	3	6	1	1	2	2	2	2	3
13	1.06967	1.07286	1.07603	1.07918	1.08231	1.08541	1.08848	1.09154	1.09457	1.09758	4	7	0	4	7	1	4	0	1
14	1.10057	1.10354	1.10649	1.10941	1.11232	1.11521	1.11807	1.12092	1.12375	1.12656	3	6	1	1	1	2	2	2	3
15	1.12934	1.13212	1.13487	1.1376	1.14032	1.14302	1.1457	1.14837	1.15101	1.15364	1	2	5	8	1	1	1	2	2
16	1.15626	1.15886	1.16144	1.16401	1.16656	1.16909	1.17161	1.17412	1.17661	1.17908	2	5	7	1	7	2	7	5	8
17	1.18154	1.18399	1.18642	1.18884	1.19124	1.19363	1.19601	1.19837	1.20072	1.20306	4	8	2	6	9	3	7	3	5
18	1.20538	1.20769	1.20999	1.21227	1.21454	1.21680	1.21905	1.22129	1.22351	1.22573	2	4	6	9	1	3	5	8	3
19	1.22793	1.23012	1.23229	1.23446	1.23661	1.23876	1.24089	1.24301	1.24513	1.24723	3	5	8	0	3	5	8	3	3
20	1.24932	1.25140	1.25347	1.25553	1.25758	1.25962	1.26164	1.26366	1.26567	1.26767	2	4	6	8	0	2	5	7	9
21	1.26966	1.27165	1.27362	1.27558	1.27753	1.27948	1.28141	1.28334	1.28526	1.28716	0	1	1	2	2	3	5	8	3
22	1.28906	1.29096	1.29284	1.29471	1.29658	1.29844	1.30029	1.30213	1.30396	1.30579	1	3	5	7	9	1	3	5	7
23	1.30760	1.30941	1.31121	1.31301	1.31479	1.31657	1.31834	1.32011	1.32186	1.32361	9	7	6	4	3	1	0	7	5

24	1.32535	1.32709	1.32881	1.33053	1.33224	1.33395	1.33565	1.33734	1.33903	1.3407	1	3	5	6	8	1	1	1	1
25	1.34238	1.34404	1.34570	1.34735	1.34900	1.35063	1.35227	1.35389	1.35551	1.35712	1	3	4	6	8	9	1	1	1
26	1.35873	1.36033	1.36193	1.36352	1.36510	1.36668	1.36825	1.36981	1.37137	1.37292	1	3	4	6	7	9	1	1	1
27	1.37447	1.37601	1.37755	1.37908	1.38060	1.38212	1.38364	1.38514	1.38665	1.38815	1	3	4	6	7	9	1	1	1
28	1.38964	1.39112	1.39261	1.39408	1.39555	1.39702	1.39848	1.39993	1.40139	1.40283	1	2	4	5	7	8	1	1	1
29	1.40427	1.40571	1.40714	1.40856	1.40998	1.41140	1.41281	1.41422	1.41562	1.41702	1	2	4	5	7	8	9	1	1
30	1.41841	1.41980	1.42118	1.42256	1.42393	1.42530	1.42667	1.42803	1.42938	1.43074	1	2	4	5	6	8	9	1	1
31	1.43208	1.43343	1.43477	1.43610	1.43743	1.43876	1.44008	1.44140	1.44271	1.44402	1	2	4	5	6	7	9	1	1
32	1.44532	1.44663	1.44792	1.44922	1.45050	1.45179	1.45307	1.45435	1.45562	1.45689	1	2	3	5	6	7	9	1	1
33	1.45816	1.45942	1.46068	1.46193	1.46318	1.46443	1.46567	1.46691	1.46815	1.46938	1	2	3	5	6	7	8	1	1
34	1.47061	1.47183	1.47305	1.47427	1.47548	1.47669	1.47790	1.47911	1.48031	1.48150	1	2	3	4	6	7	8	9	1
35	1.48270	1.48389	1.48507	1.48625	1.48743	1.48861	1.48978	1.49095	1.49212	1.49328	1	2	3	4	5	7	8	9	1
36	1.49444	1.49560	1.49675	1.49790	1.49905	1.50020	1.50134	1.50247	1.50361	1.50474	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	9	1
37	1.50587	1.50700	1.50812	1.50924	1.51035	1.51147	1.51258	1.51369	1.51479	1.51589	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	9	1
38	1.51699	1.51809	1.51918	1.52027	1.52136	1.52244	1.52352	1.52460	1.52568	1.52675	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
39	1.52782	1.52889	1.52996	1.53102	1.53208	1.53314	1.53419	1.53524	1.53629	1.53734	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
40	1.53838	1.53942	1.54046	1.54150	1.54253	1.54356	1.54459	1.54562	1.54664	1.54766	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
41	1.54868	1.54970	1.55071	1.55172	1.55273	1.55373	1.54774	1.55574	1.55674	1.55774	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
42	1.55873	1.55972	1.56071	1.56170	1.56268	1.56366	1.56464	1.56562	1.56666	1.56757	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
43	1.56854	1.56951	1.57048	1.57144	1.57240	1.57336	1.57432	1.57528	1.57623	1.57718	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
44	1.57813	1.57908	1.58002	1.58096	1.58190	1.58284	1.58378	1.58471	1.58564	1.58657	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
45	1.58750	1.58843	1.58935	1.59027	1.59119	1.59211	1.59303	1.59394	1.59485	1.59576	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
46	1.59667	1.59757	1.59848	1.59938	1.60028	1.60118	1.60207	1.60297	1.60386	1.60475	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
47	1.60564	1.60652	1.60741	1.60829	1.60917	1.61005	1.61093	1.6118	1.61267	1.61355	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
48	1.61442	1.61528	1.61615	1.61701	1.61788	1.61874	1.61960	1.62045	1.62131	1.62216	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
49	1.62302	1.62387	1.62471	1.62556	1.62641	1.62725	1.62809	1.62893	1.62977	1.63061	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
50	1.63144	1.63227	1.63311	1.63394	1.63476	1.63559	1.63641	1.63724	1.63806	1.63888	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
51	1.63970	1.64052	1.64133	1.64214	1.64296	1.64377	1.64458	1.64538	1.64619	1.64699	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
52	1.64780	1.64860	1.64940	1.65020	1.65099	1.65179	1.65258	1.65337	1.65416	1.65495	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
53	1.65574	1.65653	1.65731	1.65809	1.65888	1.65966	1.66043	1.66121	1.66199	1.66276	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
54	1.66354	1.66431	1.66508	1.66585	1.66661	1.66738	1.66814	1.66891	1.66967	1.67043	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
55	1.67119	1.67195	1.67270	1.67346	1.67421	1.67496	1.67571	1.67646	1.67721	1.67796	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
56	1.67870	1.67945	1.68019	1.68093	1.68167	1.68241	1.68315	1.68388	1.68462	1.68535	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
57	1.68608	1.68681	1.68754	1.68827	1.68900	1.68973	1.69045	1.69117	1.6919	1.69262	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
58	1.69334	1.69405	1.69477	1.69549	1.69620	1.69692	1.69763	1.69834	1.69905	1.69976	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
59	1.70047	1.70117	1.70188	1.70258	1.70328	1.70398	1.70468	1.70538	1.70608	1.70678	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
60	1.70747	1.70817	1.70886	1.70955	1.71025	1.71094	1.71162	1.71231	1.713	1.71368	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
61	1.71437	1.71505	1.71573	1.71641	1.71709	1.71777	1.71845	1.71913	1.7198	1.72048	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
62	1.72115	1.72182	1.72249	1.72316	1.72383	1.72450	1.72517	1.72583	1.7265	1.72716	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
63	1.72782	1.72848	1.72914	1.72980	1.73046	1.73112	1.73177	1.73243	1.73308	1.73374	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
64	1.73439	1.73504	1.73569	1.73634	1.73699	1.73763	1.73828	1.73893	1.73957	1.74021	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
65	1.74085	1.74150	1.74214	1.74278	1.74341	1.74405	1.74469	1.74532	1.74596	1.74659	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
66	1.74722	1.74785	1.74848	1.74911	1.74974	1.75037	1.75100	1.75162	1.75225	1.75287	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
67	1.75349	1.75411	1.75474	1.75536	1.75598	1.75659	1.75721	1.75783	1.75844	1.75906	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
68	1.75967	1.76028	1.76089	1.76151	1.76212	1.76273	1.76333	1.76394	1.76455	1.76515	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
69	1.76576	1.76636	1.76697	1.76757	1.76817	1.76877	1.76937	1.76997	1.77057	1.77116	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1
70	1.77176	1.77236	1.77295	1.77354	1.77414	1.77473	1.77532	1.77591	1.7765	1.77709	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	1

0.05	1.12738	1.13008	1.1328	1.13552	1.13824	1.14098	1.14372	1.14646	1.14921	1.15197	2	7	5	8	1	1	1	1	2	2	4
0.06	1.15474	1.15751	1.16029	1.16308	1.16587	1.16867	1.17147	1.17428	1.17710	1.17993	2	8	5	8	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.07	1.18276	1.1856	1.18845	1.19130	1.19416	1.19703	1.19990	1.20278	1.20567	1.20857	2	9	5	8	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.08	1.21147	1.21437	1.21729	1.22021	1.22314	1.22608	1.22902	1.23197	1.23493	1.2379	2	9	5	8	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.09	1.24087	1.24385	1.24683	1.24983	1.25283	1.25583	1.25885	1.26187	1.26490	1.26794	3	0	6	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.10	1.27098	1.27493	1.27709	1.28016	1.28323	1.28631	1.28940	1.2925	1.29560	1.29871	3	1	6	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.11	1.30183	1.30495	1.30809	1.31123	1.31437	1.31753	1.32069	1.32386	1.32704	1.33023	3	2	6	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.12	1.33342	1.33662	1.33983	1.34305	1.34627	1.34950	1.35274	1.35599	1.35925	1.36251	3	2	6	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.13	1.36578	1.36906	1.37235	1.37564	1.37894	1.38225	1.38557	1.38890	1.39223	1.39558	3	3	6	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.14	1.39893	1.40229	1.40565	1.40903	1.41241	1.41580	1.41920	1.42261	1.42602	1.42945	3	4	6	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.15	1.43288	1.43632	1.43977	1.44322	1.44669	1.45016	1.45364	1.45713	1.46063	1.46414	3	5	6	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.16	1.46765	1.47117	1.47471	1.47825	1.48180	1.48535	1.48892	1.49249	1.49608	1.49967	3	6	7	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.17	1.50327	1.50688	1.51050	1.51412	1.51776	1.52140	1.52505	1.52871	1.53239	1.53606	3	6	7	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.18	1.53975	1.54345	1.54715	1.55087	1.55459	1.55832	1.56206	1.56581	1.56957	1.57334	3	7	7	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.19	1.57712	1.58091	1.58470	1.58851	1.59232	1.59614	1.59997	1.60382	1.60767	1.61153	3	8	7	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.20	1.61539	1.61927	1.62316	1.62706	1.63096	1.63488	1.63880	1.64274	1.64668	1.65064	3	9	7	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.21	1.65460	1.65857	1.66255	1.66654	1.67054	1.67456	1.67858	1.68261	1.68664	1.69069	4	0	8	0	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.22	1.69475	1.69882	1.70290	1.70699	1.71109	1.71519	1.71931	1.72344	1.72758	1.73172	4	1	8	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.23	1.73588	1.74005	1.74423	1.74841	1.75261	1.75682	1.76104	1.76527	1.76950	1.77375	4	2	8	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.24	1.77801	1.78228	1.78656	1.79085	1.79515	1.79946	1.80378	1.80811	1.81245	1.81680	4	3	8	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.25	1.82116	1.82553	1.82992	1.83431	1.83871	1.84313	1.84755	1.85199	1.85643	1.86089	4	4	8	3	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.26	1.86536	1.86984	1.87432	1.87882	1.88334	1.88786	1.89239	1.89693	1.90149	1.90605	4	5	9	3	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.27	1.91063	1.91521	1.91981	1.92442	1.92904	1.93367	1.93832	1.94297	1.94763	1.95231	4	6	9	3	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.28	1.95700	1.96169	1.96640	1.97112	1.97586	1.9806	1.98536	1.99012	1.99490	1.99969	4	7	9	4	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.29	2.00449	2.00930	2.01413	2.01896	2.02381	2.02867	2.03354	2.03842	2.04331	2.04822	4	8	9	4	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.30	2.05314	2.05807	2.06301	2.06796	2.07292	2.07790	2.08289	2.08789	2.09290	2.09793	5	0	0	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.31	2.10296	2.10801	2.11307	2.11815	2.12323	2.12833	2.13344	2.13856	2.14369	2.14884	5	1	0	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.32	2.15400	2.15917	2.16435	2.16955	2.17476	2.17998	2.18521	2.19046	2.19572	2.20099	5	2	0	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.33	2.20627	2.21157	2.21688	2.22220	2.22754	2.23289	2.23825	2.24362	2.24901	2.25441	5	3	0	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.34	2.25982	2.26524	2.27068	2.27613	2.28160	2.28708	2.29257	2.29807	2.30359	2.30912	5	4	0	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.35	2.31466	2.32022	2.32579	2.33137	2.33697	2.34258	2.34820	2.35384	2.35949	2.36516	5	5	0	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.36	2.37084	2.37653	2.38223	2.38795	2.39368	2.39943	2.40519	2.41097	2.41675	2.42256	5	6	0	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.37	2.42837	2.43420	2.44005	2.4459	2.45178	2.45766	2.46356	2.46948	2.47541	2.48135	5	7	0	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.38	2.48731	2.49328	2.49926	2.50526	2.51128	2.51731	2.52335	2.52941	2.53548	2.54157	6	0	0	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.39	2.54767	2.55379	2.55992	2.56606	2.57222	2.57840	2.58459	2.59079	2.59701	2.60325	6	1	0	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.40	2.6095	2.61576	2.62204	2.62834	2.63465	2.64097	2.64731	2.65367	2.66004	2.66643	6	2	0	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
0.41	2.67283	2.67924	2.68568	2.69212	2.69859	2.70507	2.71156	2.71807	2.72460	2.73114	6	3	0	9	1	1	1	1	2	2	2

Table 8. Conversion of 11^y to 10^n in Four Figures $11^y \rightarrow 10^n$.

11^y	10^n	11^y	10^n	11^y	10^n	11^y	10^n	11^y	10^n
y = 1	n = 1.04139	y = 21	n = 21.86925	y = 41	n = 42.69710	y = 61	n = 63.52495	y = 81	n = 84.35281
2	2.08279	22	22.91064	42	43.73849	62	64.56635	82	85.39420
3	3.12418	23	23.95203	43	44.77989	63	65.60774	83	86.43559
4	4.16557	24	24.99342	44	45.82128	64	66.64913	84	87.47699
5	5.20696	25	26.03482	45	46.86267	65	67.69052	85	88.51838
6	6.24836	26	27.07621	46	47.90406	66	68.73192	86	89.55977
7	7.28975	27	28.11760	47	48.94546	67	69.77331	87	90.60116
8	8.33114	28	29.15900	48	49.98685	68	70.81470	88	91.64256
9	9.37253	29	30.20039	49	51.02824	69	71.85610	89	92.68395
10	10.41393	30	31.24178	50	52.06963	70	72.89749	90	93.72534
11	11.45532	31	32.28317	51	53.11103	71	73.93888	91	94.76673
12	12.49671	32	33.32457	52	54.15242	72	74.98027	92	95.80813
13	13.53810	33	34.36596	53	55.19381	73	76.02167	93	96.84952
14	14.57950	34	35.40735	54	56.23520	74	77.06306	94	97.89091
15	15.62089	35	36.44874	55	57.27660	75	78.10445	95	98.93231
16	15.66228	36	37.49014	56	58.31799	76	79.14584	96	99.97370
17	17.70368	37	38.53153	57	59.35938	77	80.18724	97	101.01509
18	18.74507	38	39.57292	58	60.40078	78	81.22863	98	102.05648
19	19.78646	39	40.61431	59	61.44217	79	82.27002	99	103.09788
20	20.82785	40	41.65571	60	62.48356	80	83.11410		

2.1. The Analysis of the u “Difference” Section of the Four and Five Figures of Kifilideen (Power of Base 11) and Antikifilideen (Antipower of Base 11) Tables

The analysis of number of one, two, three and four digits in all the boxes of the “difference” section of the four and five figures of Kifilideen (power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables was carried out. The analysis was carried to quantify the numbers of one, two, three and four digits contain in all the boxes of the four and five figures of Kifilideen (power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables. The analysis would show the table with higher number of small digits in all the boxes of the “difference” section of the Kifilideen (power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables. The table with the highest percentage of small digits in all the boxes of the “difference” section of the Kifilideen (power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables would be easy to compute during mathematical computation. The formula below was used to determine the percentage of the number of a particular digit contains in the total number of boxes in the “difference” section of the Kifilideen (power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables.

$$\% \text{ number of a particular digit} = \frac{\text{number of a particular digit}}{\text{total number of boxes in the "difference" section of the table}} \times 100 \% \tag{1}$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Kifilideen was the first scholar to establish and publish five figure tables of power of bases (2, 5 and 11) and antipower of bases (2, 5 and 11) as a tool to solve mathematical problems (Osanyinpeju, 2019, Osanyinpeju et al., 2019, Osanyinpeju, 2020). The idea of the establishment of the five-figure table is to have more accurate figures. As it is known that the more the approximation to lesser figures the more the error when the lesser figure is used for computation.

Although lesser figure is very easy to compute and work with. For example, for four figure table $11^{1.5781}$ or $11^{1.5782}$ gives 43.9969 or 44.0074 $\approx$ **44** while for five figure table $11^{1.57813}$ gives exact 44.0000.

The establishment of logarithms, reciprocal, sine, cosine, and tangent tables are based on four figure tables. They were established in that form four figure form because it helps to minimize the digits in each box of the “difference” sections of their tables which are mostly one or two digits while few of its are three digits. This makes it easy to add the “difference” to the main part of the table when the need arises. The main parts of the four-figure table of those functions (logarithms, reciprocal, sine, cosine and tangent) are four figures which take less time to work with.

Tables 9-10 present the analysis of the “difference” section of the four and five figures of Kifilideen (power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables. The analysis of the “difference” sections of the four figures tables of the power of base 11 indicate that the percentages of boxes in the “difference” sections that are one digit, two digits, three digits and four digits are 78.89 %, 21.21 %, 1.23 %, 0.00 % respectively while the five figures tables of the power of base 11 indicate that the percentages of boxes in the “difference” sections that are one digit, two digits, three digits and four digits are 7.52 %, 72.28 %, 18.97 % and 1.23 % respectively.

Table 9. The Analysis of the “Difference” Section of the Four and Five Figures of Kifilideen (Power of Base 11) Tables.

Under Difference	One digit		Two digits		Three digits		Four digits		Grand total	
	Four Figure	Five Figure								
1	96	55	03	41	00	03	00	00		
2	91	12	08	80	00	07	00	00		
3	87	00	12	87	00	12	00	00		
4	81	00	17	83	01	15	00	01		
5	77	00	21	79	01	19	00	01		
6	72	00	25	75	02	22	00	02		
7	67	00	30	71	02	26	00	02		
8	63	00	34	66	02	33	00	02		
9	57	00	39	62	03	37	00	03		
Total	691	067	189	644	011	169	000	011	891	891
%	77.89	7.52	21.21	72.28	1.23	18.97	00.00	1.23	100	100

Table 10. The Analysis of the “Difference” Section of the Four and Five Figures of AntiKifilideen (AntiPower of Base 11) Tables.

Under Difference	One digit		Two digits		Three digits		Four digits			
	<i>Four Figure</i>	<i>Five Figure</i>	<i>Four Figure</i>	<i>Five Figure</i>	<i>Four Figure</i>	<i>Five Figure</i>	<i>Four Figure</i>	<i>Five Figure</i>	<i>Four Figure</i>	<i>Five Figure</i>
1	57	00	43	59	00	41	00	00		
2	29	00	71	30	00	70	00	00		
3	12	00	88	14	00	86	00	00		
4	00	00	98	02	02	96	00	02		
5	00	00	89	00	11	88	00	12		
6	00	00	81	00	19	81	00	19		
7	00	00	74	00	26	74	00	26		
8	00	00	69	00	31	69	00	31		
9	00	00	64	00	36	64	00	36		
Total	098	000	677	105	125	669	000	126	900	900
%	10.89	00	75.22	11.67	13.89	74.33	00	14.00	100	100

More so, The analysis of the “difference” sections of the four figures tables of the antipower of base 11 show that the percentages of boxes in the “difference” sections that are one digit, two digits, three digits and four digits are 10.89 %, 75.22 %, 13.89 %, 0.00 % respectively while the five figures table of the power of base 11 indicate that the percentages of boxes in the “difference” sections that are one digit, two digits, three digits and four digits are 0.00 %, 11.67 %, 74.33 % and 14.00 % respectively.

So, there is a trade off when making decision on using four and five figure tables. Both the four and five figure tables give accurate and reliable results although the five figures are more accurate than the four figure tables, while the four figures are easier to work with. This indicates that there is need to create four figure tables for easy synchronization with existing Logarithm table of power of base 10 which is working on four figures.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the four and five figures of Kifilideen (Power of base 11) and AntiKifilideen (Antipower of base 11) tables for the computation of mathematical problem. The four and five

figures are both reliable to work with. However, there is a tradeoff between easy computation as related to four figure table and more accuracy as related to five figure table in their utilization.

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